

Studies on evaluation and performance of ratoon crop of selected induced mutant genotypes of banana

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Introduction

Banana (*Musa spp.*) is a vital tropical fruit crop with high nutritional and economic value, ranking fourth globally among food crops. It is

rich in carbohydrates, fiber, and essential minerals, making it important for food security and therapeutic diets. Most edible bananas are hybrids of *Musa acuminata* and *M. balbisiana*,

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Abstract

The present investigation titled "Studies on evaluation and performance of ratoon crop of selected induced mutant genotypes of banana" was conducted during the academic year 2024-2025 at the Research Farm, Department of Horticulture, VNMKV, Parbhani to evaluate the ratoon crop performance of seven induced banana mutants (M₃, M₅, M₆, M₈, M₁₀, M₁₄, M₁₅) along with the control (Grand Naine). Significant variation was observed among genotypes for growth, flowering, finger, and bunch traits. The tallest plants were recorded in T₈ (Grand Naine) (193.89 cm), while T₁ (M₃) produced the highest number of leaves (14.40). T₈ also showed maximum pseudostem girth (70.66 cm) and leaf area (11.33 cm²). Early flowering was noted in T₁ (M₃), with minimum days to flowering (168.46), fruit maturity (94.58), and total crop duration (263.04 days). T₁ (M₃) also recorded the highest finger length (20.14 cm), finger girth (13.04 cm), finger weight (185.45 g), bunch weight (26.12 kg) and bunch length (76.84 cm). Number of hands per bunch showed no significant difference across treatments. Overall, T₁ (M₃) emerged as the most promising genotype for key agronomic traits in ratoon cropping.

Keywords: Banana, mutants, genotypes, ratoon, grand naine

grouped into genomic categories such as AA, AAA and ABB. In India, banana is the second most cultivated fruit after mango, with Maharashtra being a major producer. The Grand Naine variety dominates due to its high yield and export value, though it suffers from limitations like tall stature, lodging susceptibility and long crop duration. In vitro mutagenesis is a promising tool for improving traits such as dwarfness, early maturity and stress tolerance. Ratooning, where new crops arise from the suckers of harvested plants is widely practiced to reduce costs and improve land use efficiency, but its success depends on proper management and the use of vigorous genotypes. Identifying improved mutant lines with better ratoon performance is crucial for enhancing productivity and sustainability in banana cultivation.

Materials and Methods

The present investigation titled "Studies on evaluation and performance of ratoon crop of selected induced mutant genotypes of banana" was conducted during the academic year 2024-2025 at the Research Farm, Department of Horticulture, VNMKV, Parbhani. The experiment was laid out in a Randomized Block Design (RBD) with the treatments included seven induced mutant genotypes M₃ (T₁), M₅ (T₂), M₆ (T₃), M₈ (T₄), M₁₀ (T₅), M₁₄ (T₆) and M₁₅ (T₇) along with the standard cultivar Grand Naine as the control (T₈). Planting was done at a spacing of 1.5 m × 1.5 m using uniform, disease-free tissue-cultured plantlets. The ratoon crop was raised by allowing regrowth from the previously harvested mother plants after appropriate agronomic management. Observations were recorded on various growth parameters (such as plant height, pseudostem girth, number of functional leaves), yield attributes (like number of hands per bunch, number of fingers per hand and bunch weight) Data were statistically analyzed to assess the performance and variability among treatments.

Results and Discussion

The results of the present investigation are presented in accordance with the objectives outlined below to study the ratoon crop performance of selected induced mutants of banana.

A) Growth parameters

The data pertaining to growth parameters *viz.*, plant height, number of leaves per plant, pseudo stem girth and leaf area (cm²) of the selected induced mutant genotypes of banana under field conditions have been recorded and are presented under relevant headings.

4.1.1. Plant height (cm)

The plant height of the ratoon crop showed significant genotypic variation, ranging from 138.22 cm to 193.89 cm, with a mean of 162.97 cm). The tallest plants were observed in T₈ [Grand Naine (control)] (193.89 cm), followed by T₇ [M₁₅] (173.98 cm), T₅ [M₁₀] (170.16 cm), T₆ [M₁₄] (168.31 cm) and T₁ [M₃] (162.33 cm), all statistically comparable. The shortest height was recorded in T₃ [M₆] (138.22 cm), which was statistically similar to T₄ [M₈] (144.22 cm) and T₂ [M₅] (152.66 cm). The variation in plant height may be attributed to genotypic differences, consistent with findings by Devi et al. (2011), Mahmoud and Gaffar (2013), Bhanusree et al. (2015), Kalalbandi (2017), and Mattos et al. (2010).

Table 4.1: Performance of ratoon crop of selected induced mutant genotypes of banana in respect of plant height (cm)

Treatments	Mutant genotypes	Plant height (cm)
T ₁	M ₃	162.33
T ₂	M ₅	152.66
T ₃	M ₆	138.22
T ₄	M ₈	144.22
T ₅	M ₁₀	170.16
T ₆	M ₁₄	168.31
T ₇	M ₁₅	173.98
T ₈	Grand Naine (Control)	193.89
Mean		162.97

S.E. (m) (\pm)	4.37
C.D. @ 5%	13.26

4.1.2. Number of leaves plant⁻¹

Significant variation in the number of leaves per plant was observed among the ratoon crop genotypes, ranged from 11.66 to 14.40, with a mean of 13.22 leaves. T₁ [M₃] recorded the highest leaf count (14.40), significantly outperformed other genotypes. This was followed by T₈ [Grand Naine (control)] (14.12), T₅ [M₁₀] (13.80), T₇ [M₁₅] (13.33) and T₆ [M₁₄] (13.20), all statistically on par. The lowest leaf count was noted in T₃ [M₆] (11.66), comparable to T₄ [M₈] (12.40) and T₂ [M₅] (12.88). These results suggest enhanced vegetative growth in certain mutants, notably T₁ [M₃]. Similar genotypic differences in leaf production were reported by Biswal *et al.* (2004), Tak *et al.* (2015), Dhole *et al.* (2024) and Medhi (1994).

Table 4.2: Performance of ratoon crop of selected induced mutant genotypes of banana in respect of number of leaves plant⁻¹

Treatments	Mutant genotypes	Number of leaves plant ⁻¹
T ₁	M ₃	14.40
T ₂	M ₅	12.88
T ₃	M ₆	11.66
T ₄	M ₈	12.40
T ₅	M ₁₀	13.80
T ₆	M ₁₄	13.20
T ₇	M ₁₅	13.33
T ₈	Grand Naine (Control)	14.12
Mean		13.22
S.E. (m) (\pm)		0.40
C.D. @ 5%		1.23

4.1.3. Girth of pseudo stem (cm)

Statistical analysis revealed significant differences in pseudostem girth among the ratoon crop genotypes, with values ranged from 62.03 cm to 70.66 cm and a mean of 65.42 cm. The highest girth was recorded in T₈ [Grand Naine (control)] (70.66 cm), followed by T₁ [M₃] (67.17 cm) and T₅ [M₁₀] (66.57 cm), while the lowest

was observed in T₂ [M₅] (62.03 cm). The observed variation may be attributed to genotypic and environmental factors. These results are consistent with the findings of Lenka and Lenka (2014), Navaneethakrishnan *et al.* (2013) and Biswal *et al.* (2004), who reported similar genotypic differences in pseudostem girth.

Table 4.3: Performance of ratoon crop of selected induced mutant genotypes of banana in respect of girth of pseudo stem

Treatments	Mutant genotypes	Girth of pseudo stem (cm)
T ₁	M ₃	67.17
T ₂	M ₅	62.03
T ₃	M ₆	63.17
T ₄	M ₈	63.90
T ₅	M ₁₀	66.57
T ₆	M ₁₄	63.66
T ₇	M ₁₅	66.20
T ₈	Grand Naine (Control)	70.66
Mean		65.42
S.E. (m) (\pm)		0.61
C.D. @ 5%		1.85

4.1.4. Leaf area (cm²)

Statistical analysis revealed significant variation in leaf area among the ratoon crop genotypes, ranged from 5.30 cm² to 11.33 cm², with a mean of 9.03 cm². The highest leaf area was observed in T₈ [Grand Naine (control)] (11.33 cm²), followed by T₆ [M₁₄] (11.25 cm²), T₁ [M₃] (10.78 cm²), T₇ [M₁₅] (10.20 cm²) and T₅ [M₁₀] (9.64 cm²), all statistically at par. The lowest values were recorded in T₃ [M₆] (5.30 cm²), T₂ [M₅] (6.84 cm²) and T₄ [M₈] (6.94 cm²). These results support previous findings by Tak *et al.* (2015), who reported a positive correlation between plant height and leaf area and align with earlier observations on genotypic variation in leaf traits by Smith *et al.* (2014) and Rajamanickam and Rajmohan (2010).

Table 4.4: Performance of ratoon crop of selected induced mutant genotypes of banana in respect of leaf area (cm²)

Treatments	Mutant genotypes	Leaf area (cm ²)
T ₁	M ₃	10.78
T ₂	M ₅	6.80
T ₃	M ₆	5.30
T ₄	M ₈	6.94
T ₅	M ₁₀	9.64
T ₆	M ₁₄	11.25
T ₇	M ₁₅	10.20
T ₈	Grand Naine (Control)	11.33
Mean		9.03
S.E. (m) (±)		0.40
C.D. @ 5%		1.23

C) Shooting parameters

Data related to shooting parameters including Days taken to flowering, Days taken from flowering to maturity, Crop duration (days) and Number of suckers per plant were recorded for the ratoon crop of selected induced mutant genotypes of banana under field conditions. These results were organized and presented under the relevant sections.

4.2.1. Days taken to flowering

Statistical analysis revealed significant variation in days to flowering among the induced mutant genotypes, which ranged from 168.42 to 194.94 days, with a mean of 181.00 days. The earliest flowering was recorded in T₁ (M₃) with 168.46 days, which significantly outperformed the other genotypes. This was followed by T₅ (M₁₀) with 174.77 days, T₆ (M₁₄) with 178.57 days and T₄ (M₈) with 178.64 days; all of these were statistically at par. The longest duration to flowering was observed in T₈ Grand Naine (control) with 194.94 days, which was statistically comparable to T₃ (M₆) with 186.55 days. The early flowering observed in M₃ was likely due to beneficial genetic alterations induced through mutation. These findings were consistent with those reported by Gawade (2021),

who noted similar trends in ratoon crop performance and Chhuria *et al.* (2016), who reported a minimum of 201.7 days to flowering among Grand Naine genotypes, supported the observed genotypic variability.

Table 4.5: Performance of ratoon crop of selected induced mutant genotypes of banana in respect of days taken to flowering

Treatments	Mutant genotypes	Days taken to flowering
T ₁	M ₃	168.46
T ₂	M ₅	185.30
T ₃	M ₆	186.55
T ₄	M ₈	178.64
T ₅	M ₁₀	174.77
T ₆	M ₁₄	178.57
T ₇	M ₁₅	180.77
T ₈	Grand Naine (Control)	194.94
Mean		181.00
S.E. (m) (±)		2.59
C.D. @ 5%		7.87

4.2.2. Days taken from flowering to maturity

The analysis of flowering-to-maturity duration revealed significant differences among the genotypes, with values ranged from 94.58 to 110.28 days and a mean of 105.68 days. The shortest duration was observed in T₁ (M₃) with 94.58 days, which matured significantly earlier than all other treatments. This was followed by T₂ (M₅), which recorded 103.80 days. The longest period to maturity was recorded in T₈ Grand Naine (control) with 110.28 days, which was statistically comparable to T₄ (M₈) with 108.53 days, T₇ (M₁₅) with 108.77 days and T₆ (M₁₄) with 107.21 days. These results aligned with the observations of Kalalbandi (2017), who reported similar genotypic differences in maturity duration. Digal (2016) also reported a minimum of 90.60 days from flowering to harvest in certain banana genotypes, supported the present findings.

Table 4.6: Performance of ratoon crop of selected induced mutant genotypes of banana in respect of days taken from flowering to maturity

Treatments	Mutant genotypes	Days taken from flowering to maturity
T ₁	M ₃	94.58
T ₂	M ₅	103.80
T ₃	M ₆	106.64
T ₄	M ₈	108.53
T ₅	M ₁₀	105.40
T ₆	M ₁₄	107.21
T ₇	M ₁₅	108.66
T ₈	Grand Naine (Control)	110.28
Mean		105.63
S.E. (m) (±)		2.80
C.D. @ 5%		8.51

4.2.3. Crop duration (days)

The crop duration across genotypes ranged from 263.04 to 305.22 days, with an overall mean of 286.11 days. Among the treatments, T₁ [M₃] recorded the shortest crop duration of 263.04 days, clearly indicated its advantage in earliness over the other genotypes. It was closely followed by T₅ [M₁₀], which showed duration of 280.17 days. In contrast, the longest crop duration was observed in T₈ [Grand Naine (control)] (305.22 days), suggested delayed maturity. Crop duration in banana is influenced by the time taken from planting to shooting and from shooting to harvesting. Among these two phases, greater variation was observed in the planting to shooting period, highlighted it as the key contributor to overall crop duration variability. These findings aligned with earlier studies. Kanamadi *et al.* (2002) reported early shooting in 'Dwarf Cavendish' at 246 days, while 'Red Banana' exhibited delayed shooting at 384 days. Similarly, Borah *et al.* (2018) observed early shooting at 277.72 days and delayed shooting at 321.05 days in the cultivar 'Malbhog' (AAB group) under ratoon crop conditions.

Table 4.7: Performance of ratoon crop of selected induced mutant genotypes of banana in respect of crop duration (days)

Treatments	Mutant genotypes	Crop duration (days)
T ₁	M ₃	263.04
T ₂	M ₅	289.20
T ₃	M ₆	289.19
T ₄	M ₈	287.17
T ₅	M ₁₀	280.17
T ₆	M ₁₄	285.78
T ₇	M ₁₅	289.17
T ₈	Grand Naine (Control)	305.22
Mean		286.11
S.E. (m) (±)		1.57
C.D. @ 5%		4.76

4.2.4. Number of suckers plant⁻¹

The analysis revealed that the differences among the genotypes were not statistically significant. Despite this, the number of suckers per plant varied slightly, ranged from 4.16 to 4.62, with an overall mean of 4.37. Among the genotypes, the highest number of suckers per plant was observed in T₆ [M₁₄] (4.62), while the lowest was recorded in T₁ [M₃] (4.16). These findings were in line with the observations reported by Bhende & Kurien (2016) and Dhole *et al.* (2024) suggested consistency in sucker production trends across similar genotypic variations.

Table 4.8: Performance of ratoon crop of selected induced mutant genotypes of banana in respect of number of suckers plant⁻¹

Treatments	Mutant genotypes	Number of suckers plant ⁻¹
T ₁	M ₃	4.16
T ₂	M ₅	4.35
T ₃	M ₆	4.37
T ₄	M ₈	4.22
T ₅	M ₁₀	4.25
T ₆	M ₁₄	4.62
T ₇	M ₁₅	4.59
T ₈	Grand Naine (Control)	4.47
Mean		4.37

S.E. (m) (±)	0.20
C.D. @ 5%	NS

C) Finger characters

4.3.1. Length of finger (cm)

Finger length in the ratoon crop of selected induced mutant genotypes of banana showed significant variation ranged from 15.30 cm to 20.14 cm with a mean of 17.66 cm. The longest fingers were observed in genotype T₁ [M₃] (20.14 cm), followed by T₈ [Grand Naine (control)] (19.25 cm), with both being statistically at par. The shortest finger length was recorded in T₃ [M₆] (15.30 cm), which was statistically similar to T₂ [M₅] (16.20 cm) and T₄ [M₈] (16.78 cm). The variation may be attributed to genotypic differences, particularly the influence of *Musa acuminata* traits associated with longer fingers. These results align with earlier findings by Navaneethakrishnan *et al.* (2013), Pujari *et al.* (2010), Smith *et al.* (2014) and Dhole *et al.* (2024).

Table 4.9: Performance of ratoon crop of selected induced mutant genotypes of banana in respect of length of finger (cm)

Treatments	Mutant genotypes	Length of finger (cm)
T ₁	M ₃	20.14
T ₂	M ₅	16.20
T ₃	M ₆	15.30
T ₄	M ₈	16.78
T ₅	M ₁₀	19.20
T ₆	M ₁₄	17.12
T ₇	M ₁₅	17.35
T ₈	Grand Naine (Control)	19.25
Mean		17.66
S.E. (m) (±)		0.61
C.D. @ 5%		1.85

4.3.2. Girth of finger (cm)

The analysis revealed significant variation in finger girth among the genotypes studied. The values ranged from 10.06 cm to 13.04 cm, with an overall mean of 11.45 cm. Among the genotypes, T₁ [M₃] recorded the maximum finger girth (13.04 cm), outperformed the others in this regard. This was closely followed by T₈ [Grand Naine (control)] (12.25 cm) was found to be statistically comparable with T₁ [M₃]. On the other hand, the minimum finger girth was noted in T₃ [M₆] (10.02 cm), which was statistically at par with T₂ [M₅] (10.06 cm). These findings were in line with the observations reported by Bhagat *et al.* (2017), Borthakur *et al.* (2018) and Kalalbandi (2017) who also documented considerable variation in finger girth among different banana genotypes.

Table 4.10: Performance of ratoon crop of selected induced mutant genotypes of banana in respect of girth of finger (cm)

Treatments	Mutant genotypes	Girth of finger (cm)
T ₁	M ₃	13.04
T ₂	M ₅	10.06
T ₃	M ₆	10.02
T ₄	M ₈	11.25
T ₅	M ₁₀	11.45
T ₆	M ₁₄	11.52
T ₇	M ₁₅	12.02
T ₈	Grand Naine (Control)	12.25
Mean		11.45
S.E. (m) (±)		0.53
C.D. @ 5%		1.62

4.3.3. Weight of finger (g)

The finger weight among genotypes ranged from 125.64 g to 185.45 g, with an overall mean of 152.36 g. The genotype T₁ [M₃] exhibited the highest finger weight (185.45 g), outperformed all other genotypes in the study. This was closely followed by T₈ [Grand Naine (control)], which recorded a finger weight of 172.85 g and was statistically comparable to T₁ [M₃]. On the other hand, the lowest finger weight was recorded in T₃

[M₆] (125.64 g), which was statistically similar to T₂ [M₅] (130.23 g). The current findings were consistent with previous reports by Biswal *et al.* (2004) and Debnath *et al.* (2014) who also documented highest finger weight in banana cultivars such as Martaman.

Table 4.11: Performance of ratoon crop of selected induced mutant genotypes of banana in respect of weight of finger (g)

Treatments	Mutant genotypes	Weight of finger (g)
T ₁	M ₃	185.45
T ₂	M ₅	130.23
T ₃	M ₆	125.64
T ₄	M ₈	150.25
T ₅	M ₁₀	152.48
T ₆	M ₁₄	148.62
T ₇	M ₁₅	153.42
T ₈	Grand Naine (Control)	172.85
Mean		152.36
S.E. (m) (±)		4.08
C.D. @ 5%		12.38

C) Bunch characters

The data related to bunch characteristics namely weight of bunch (kg), length of bunch (cm) and number of hands per bunch for the ratoon crop of selected induced mutant genotypes of banana grown under field conditions were recorded and presented under their respective headings.

4.4.1 Weight of bunch (kg)

The data indicated significant variation among the genotypes, with bunch weights ranged from 15.33 kg to 26.12 kg and a mean value of 20.73 kg. Among the genotypes studied, T₁ [M₃] recorded the highest bunch weight of 26.12 kg, surpassed all others in the trial. It was followed by T₈ [Grand Naine (control)], which produced 25.33 kg. In contrast, the lowest bunch weight was observed in T₃ [M₆] (15.33 kg), which was found to be statistically at par with T₂ [M₅] (16.54 kg) and T₆ [M₁₄] (19.24 kg). The observed differences in bunch weight could be attributed to variations in bunch size, which are often

influenced by finger size. An increase in finger length and girth is likely to have contributed to higher bunch weights. These findings were in agreement with the reports of Sathish *et al.* (2021), who noted a similar relationship between finger size and bunch weight. Deshmukh *et al.* (2004) also observed maximum bunch weight in the acuminate group, while Njuguna *et al.* (2008) reported the highest bunch weight in FHIA-25, supported the present results.

Table 4.12: Performance of ratoon crop of selected induced mutant genotypes of banana in respect of weight of bunch (kg)

Treatments	Mutant genotypes	Weight of bunch (kg)
T ₁	M ₃	26.12
T ₂	M ₅	16.54
T ₃	M ₆	15.33
T ₄	M ₈	20.84
T ₅	M ₁₀	21.15
T ₆	M ₁₄	19.24
T ₇	M ₁₅	21.32
T ₈	Grand Naine (Control)	25.33
Mean		20.73
S.E. (m) (±)		0.81
C.D. @ 5%		2.46

4.4.2. Length of bunch (cm)

The recorded bunch length ranged from 54.32 cm to 76.84 cm, with an overall mean value of 66.89 cm. Among the genotypes, the longest bunch was observed in T₁ [M₃], measuring 76.84 cm, which surpassed the rest of the treatments. This was closely followed by T₈ [Grand Naine (control)] with a length of 76.28 cm and T₇ [M₁₅] with 73.64 cm, both of which were statistically comparable. On the other hand, the shortest bunch length was recorded in T₃ [M₆] at 54.32 cm, which did not differ significantly from T₂ [M₅] (58.25 cm) and T₄ [M₈] (62.51 cm). These differences in bunch length might be attributed to inherent genetic variations among the genotypes, along with factors such as the number of hands and fingers per bunch, which can directly

influence the elongation of the bunch. Similar genotypic variations in bunch length have also been documented by Digal (2016) in their study on the cultivar Grand Naine.

Table 4.13: Performance of ratoon crop of selected induced mutant genotypes of banana in respect of length of bunch (cm)

Treatments	Mutant genotypes	Length of bunch (cm)
T ₁	M ₃	76.84
T ₂	M ₅	58.25
T ₃	M ₆	54.32
T ₄	M ₈	62.51
T ₅	M ₁₀	69.84
T ₆	M ₁₄	63.44
T ₇	M ₁₅	73.64
T ₈	Grand Naine (Control)	76.28
Mean		66.89
S.E. (m) (±)		1.66
C.D. @ 5%		5.04

4.4.3. Number of hands bunch⁻¹

The number of hands per bunch ranged from 9.02 to 10.65, with an overall mean of 9.93. Among the evaluated genotypes, the highest number of hands per bunch was recorded in both T₁ [M₃] and T₈ [Grand Naine (control)], each with 10.65. This was closely followed by T₇ [M₁₅], which recorded 10.34 hands per bunch. In contrast, the lowest value was noted in T₂ [M₅], which produced 9.02 hands per bunch. These variations may be attributed to inherent genetic differences and the inheritance patterns of the respective genotypes. Comparable observations were also reported by Bhanusree *et al.* (2015) and Kalalbandi (2017) suggested consistency with earlier findings.

Table 4.14: Performance of ratoon crop of selected induced mutant genotypes of banana in respect of number of hands bunch⁻¹

Treatments	Mutant genotypes	Number of hands bunch ⁻¹
T ₁	M ₃	10.65
T ₂	M ₅	9.02
T ₃	M ₆	9.20
T ₄	M ₈	10.12
T ₅	M ₁₀	10.05
T ₆	M ₁₄	9.43
T ₇	M ₁₅	10.34
T ₈	Grand Naine (Control)	10.65
Mean		9.93
S.E. (m) (±)		0.43
C.D. @ 5%		NS

Conclusion

The present investigation on the ratoon crop of selected induced mutant genotypes of banana revealed that genotype M₃ exhibited superior performance in terms of growth, yield and economic returns. Specifically, M₃ recorded a plant height of 162.33 cm and an average bunch weight of 26.12 kg, indicated its desirable vegetative vigor and productivity even in the ratoon phase. In addition to its yield potential, M₃ demonstrated desirable bunch and finger traits making it particularly suitable for sustainable commercial cultivation. Its dwarf stature, along with its resilience and consistent performance under ratoon conditions, further supports its suitability for efficient banana production systems. Given the significance of ratoon cropping in reducing input costs and improving farm efficiency, the promising results of M₃ in the ratoon crop highlighted its value as a potential alternative to traditional banana

cultivars. To substantiate these findings, it is recommended that multi-location and multi-seasonal trials be conducted to evaluate the adaptability, stability and performance consistency of genotype M₃ across varied agro-climatic regions. Successful validation would contribute to improved productivity, profitability and sustainability of ratoon banana mutant M₃ genotype for cultivation in this region.

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